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Enhancing ICT Personnel Competencies for Green Computing Adoption in Burundian Universities

Donatien Sakubu

Student, Department of Information Technology,
Kibabii University, Kenya

Dr. Samuel Wafula Barasa

Dean, School of Computing & Informatics,
Kibabii University, Kenya

Franklin Wabwoba

Professor, Deputy Vice Chancellor (Academics, Research and Students' Affairs),
Karatina University, Kenya

Abstract:

The global need to address climate change requires the adoption of sustainable practices across all sectors, including higher education. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is crucial for university operations but significantly contributes to energy consumption and electronic waste. Green computing offers a solution by minimizing the environmental footprint of ICT. This study investigates the key factors related to ICT personnel competencies that influence the adoption of green computing practices in Burundian universities. A survey research design was employed, involving a questionnaire administered to ICT personnel across 21 universities in Burundi. Data analysis, including descriptive statistics and factor analysis, revealed that ICT skills, practical experience, professional experience, and gender significantly contribute to the capacity of ICT staff to support green computing adoption. The findings highlight the need for targeted training programs, policy interventions, and awareness campaigns to enhance these competencies and promote a culture of sustainability within Burundian higher education institutions.

Keywords: *Green computing, ICT personnel capacity, sustainable ICT, higher education, Burundi, digital sustainability, human resource development*

1. Introduction

In today's digital world, organizations, including educational institutions, heavily rely on information and communication technology (ICT) to improve efficiency, gain a competitive edge, enhance services, and achieve their goals [2]. However, the rapid growth of computing has led to increased energy consumption and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, contributing to climate change and environmental damage. According to Shearer et al. (2017), ICT contributes 2% of global CO₂ emissions due to its high energy demands [1][2][3]. This has amplified concerns about energy scarcity and electronic waste (e-waste) generation. Green computing, which aims to minimize the environmental footprint of ICT, offers a solution to these problems. It involves designing, manufacturing, using, and disposing of computer systems and related equipment in an environmentally responsible way [4][5][13]. Despite the potential benefits, higher education institutions, particularly in developing nations like Burundi, have not widely adopted green computing practices. Universities are major consumers of ICT equipment, which eventually becomes obsolete and contributes to e-waste [6][7]. They also extensively use advanced technologies for teaching and learning. Therefore, it is essential to educate and encourage staff and students to use ICT devices in a manner that reduces energy consumption and increases environmental awareness [6][7][8]. The competence of ICT personnel is vital for technological advancement and the implementation of green computing [6][7][8]. Skilled and trained staff are crucial for economic progress and technological innovation. However, there is a global shortage of green computing professionals, especially in developing countries [9][7]. The understanding and skills of an institution's ICT staff are fundamental to adopting green computing. Consequently, improving the capabilities of ICT personnel through training and practical experience is crucial for the adoption of green computing [7].

2. Statement of the Problem

Universities in Burundi have acknowledged the importance of using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to advance knowledge and benefit the community through education. While ICT offers numerous advantages, its use also raises concerns about energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions associated with the production and use of ICT devices. Despite the numerous benefits and potential of ICT in education, highlighted during the COVID-19 pandemic,

universities in Burundi have yet to fully integrate it into their service delivery. This is likely due to a lack of skilled ICT personnel in green computing. This study aims to identify the key aspects of ICT staff capacity that can facilitate the adoption of green computing in universities in Burundi.

3. Research Methodology

This study employed a survey research design, considered suitable for its adaptability and broad applicability [10]. The purpose of this design was to evaluate the factors influencing green computing adoption in Burundian universities. The study focused on the ICT departments of both public and private universities in Burundi. Factor analysis was used to identify the key variables contributing to green computing based on the collected data. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity were conducted to ensure the data was appropriate for factor analysis, yielding a value of 0.846, which indicated its suitability. Principal Component Analysis and factor rotation were then used to extract the components related to ICT personnel capacity.

4. Findings and Discussion

After performing factor analysis to completion, including rotation, several variables related to ICT personnel capacity were identified. These variables were loaded onto components 1, 4, 6, and 7 and tended to build into a similar construct as presented in table 1.

4.1. ICT Personnel Capacity

From the study findings after the final stage of factor analysis, the variables that finally loaded onto components 1, 4, 6, and 7 tended to build into a similar construct and were presented in table 1.

Loading				
Factors	1	4	6	7
PC power enforcement management	0.734			
Expertise in green computing	0.676			
Practical experience in green computing	0.852			
Working years		0.826		
Age		0.819		
Experience in ICT		0.852		
Education level			0.876	
Job position			0.828	
Gender				0.782

Table 1: Personnel Capacity Components 1, 4, 6 and 7 Factor Loadings

Based on the findings presented in table 1, The item "I do enforce PC power management (PC1)" had a factor loading of (0.734) summarized as PC power enforcement, "I am an expert in Green computing (PC2)" had a factor loading of (0.676) summarized as Expertise in green computing, "Personnel have practical experience of implementing green computing (PC5)" had a factor loading of (0.852) summarized as Practical experience in green computing. This component is loaded on component 1. This component 1 was renamed ICT skills, and weighting was taken as the average of the three items factor loading ($\frac{0.734+0.676+0.852}{3}$), yielding 0.754. the contribution of PC power enforcement management towards ICT skills is given by ($\frac{0.734}{0.734+0.676+0.852} = 0.324$), Expertise in green computing is given by ($\frac{0.676}{0.734+0.676+0.852} = 0.299$) while Practical experience in green computing is given by ($\frac{0.852}{0.734+0.676+0.852} = 0.377$). The item "working years working in the university set up" had a factor loading of (.826) summarized as working experience, "age" has a factor loading of (.819) summarized as age and "years working in ICT department" with a factor loading of (.852) summarized as experience in ICT loaded on component 4. The component 4 was renamed experience whose weighting was taken as the average of the three items factor loading ($\frac{0.826+0.819+0.852}{3}$) yielding 0.832. The contribution of working years, age and experience in ICT towards experience were respectively given by ($\frac{0.826}{0.826+0.819+0.852} = 0.331$), ($\frac{0.819}{0.826+0.819+0.852} = 0.328$) and ($\frac{0.852}{0.826+0.819+0.852} = 0.341$). The item "Level of education" had a factor loading of (0.876), summarized as education level, and "job position being held" with a factor loading of (0.828), summarized as job position loaded on component 6. The component 6 was renamed Job working status whose weighting was taken as the average of the two items factor loading ($\frac{0.876+0.828}{2}$) yielding 0.852. The contribution of education level and job position status towards working status were respectively given by ($\frac{0.876}{0.876+0.828} = 0.514$) and ($\frac{0.828}{0.876+0.828} = 0.486$). The item "Gender" had a factor loading of (0.782) and was loaded on component 7, which was renamed gender. The variables ICT skills, work experience, job working status and gender were found to contribute towards Green human ICT capacity. They were combined to form an ICT personnel capacity sub-construct.

To establish how much each of these variables contributed to the overall ICT personnel sub-construct, a ratio of the loading of each was determined in relation to their sum total loading (0.754+0.832+0.852+0.782 = 3.22). The ratio of what each contributed to the personnel capacity sub-construct was therefore calculated by dividing the sum of the average of

the loadings of the sub-construct fall under personnel capacity whereby: ICT Skills ($\frac{0.705}{3.22}$) yields (0.234), Experience ($\frac{0.832}{3.22}$) yields (0.258), Working status ($\frac{0.852}{3.22}$) yields (0.265) and Gender ($\frac{0.782}{3.22}$) yields (0.243). The findings that ICT skills are crucial align with Elsaadani's (2015) emphasis on the need for expertise in green computing for successful adoption [12]. Practical experience also emerged as a significant factor, highlighting the importance of hands-on training and implementation opportunities for ICT personnel, as suggested by Chai and Nakata [11]. The influence of working years and experience in the ICT department suggests that seasoned professionals are more likely to contribute to green computing initiatives, possibly due to their accumulated knowledge and understanding of institutional ICT infrastructure. The impact of job working status, including education level and job position, indicates that individuals in higher positions or with more education may have a greater capacity to drive and implement green computing strategies. Finally, the role of gender suggests potential differences in awareness or involvement in green computing practices, warranting further investigation. The discussion is graphically summarized as given in figure 1.

Figure 1: ICT Personnel Capacity

5. Limitations of the Study

This study specifically examined universities in Burundi, and its findings might not be directly applicable to other countries or educational settings. The sample size of 21 universities, while representing all registered institutions during the study period, is relatively small. Furthermore, the study relied on self-reported data from ICT personnel, which could be subject to personal biases.

5.1. Suggestions for Future Research

Future research could investigate the effectiveness of specific training programs designed to enhance the ICT skills identified in this study. Exploring the impact of an institution's culture and leadership on promoting green computing adoption would also be valuable. Comparative studies across different types of higher education institutions or between different countries could provide further insights into the factors that influence the adoption of green computing. Additionally, examining the perspectives of students and administrative staff on green computing initiatives could offer a more holistic understanding.

5.2. Conclusions from the Study

The findings of this study indicate that ICT skills, experience, working status, and gender are important aspects of ICT Personnel Capacity that influence the adoption of green computing in universities in Burundi. Enhancing these factors through increased awareness and opportunities for practical experience can increase the likelihood of green computing being adopted by universities in Burundi.

6. Acknowledgement

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